

The Effectiveness of Geogebra-Assisted Problem-Based Learning Model on Students' Spatial Visualization Abilities

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 26 January 2026	This study aims to determine the effectiveness of GeoGebra's problem-based learning model on spatial visualization capabilities, especially in the geometry of flat-sided spaces. This study involved 35 grade IX students in one of the public junior high schools in Bintan Regency. The study used a pre-experimental design with a one-group pretest–posttest design which aimed to explore the extent to which students' spatial visualization skills improved after GeoGebra was applied in the problem-based learning model. Data collection was carried out through spatial visualization ability tests and observation sheets used to monitor learning activities in the classroom. The results of the analysis showed that the average score of students increased by 32.50 with an average percentage of learning implementation reaching 96.42%. The results of the one sample t-test show that $t_{\text{count}} = 10,707 > t_{\text{table}} = 1,690$ and $p\text{-value} = 0,000000000000985 < 0,05$, so it can be concluded that the GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning (PBL) model is effective from the spatial visualization ability.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics learning has an important role in developing students' logical, analytical, and systematic abilities. Through mathematics learning, students are not only required to master procedures and concepts, but also to be able to relate the knowledge learned to real situations and solve complex problems. Today's mathematics learning needs to be designed in a meaningful way to be able to develop the various thinking skills needed by students to face the challenges of the 21st century. Bruner (1960) stated that mathematics learning should not only focus on existing procedures, but on understanding the concepts and structure of mathematics. Mathematics learning is no longer aimed at the process of producing the correct answers, but how students develop their thinking skills to be able to solve the problems presented (Daimah & Supardi, 2023).

However, in practice, mathematics learning in schools is still often oriented towards delivering material only and solving problems correctly. This makes students less involved in understanding mathematical concepts in depth, especially in materials that are abstract and require good visualization skills. Utami & Hendra (2020) in their research stated that without adequate spatial visualization skills, students' understanding of abstract material becomes

hampered. This is in line with Khoerulloh (2022) stating that only 52% of students can achieve the level of visualization. NCTM (2000) explained that spatial visualization ability is a cognitive ability that allows individuals to imagine, manipulate, and understand objects in three-dimensional space. Spatial visualization skills play an important role in helping students understand the relationships between objects, spatial structures, and solving geometric problems effectively.

The development of students' spatial visualization skills is inseparable from the learning process that provides space for students to actively explore and represent concepts. *Problem Based Learning* is a student-centered learning model, where students are given real problems to solve collaboratively, thus encouraging them to think critically, creatively, and independently. In *Problem Based Learning* (PBL), students are faced with complex and open problem situations, which require problem-solving through a process of investigation, discussion, and reflection (Khakim et al., 2022). Learning with Problem Based Learning provides an opportunity for students to be able to explore existing concepts in support of knowledge of these abstract concepts. To support the effectiveness of Problem Based Learning (PBL) in geometry learning, especially to facilitate

students' spatial visualization skills. The use of technology such as GeoGebra can be the right solution.

GeoGebra is a dynamic math software that integrates geometry, algebra, and calculus, allowing students to visualize and manipulate mathematical objects interactively. With the help of GeoGebra, students can more easily understand the concepts of building a flat side space through concrete and dynamic visual representations. Muliyana et al. (2022) stated that the use of GeoGebra in learning has been shown to improve concept understanding and student engagement. The use of GeoGebra also increases learning motivation (Puspasari, 2022); students' spatial abilities (Ghalib & Mahmudi, 2022). Therefore, the integration of the Problem Based Learning model with the help of GeoGebra can be a solution to improve students' spatial visualization skills and learning motivation.

By paying attention to the effectiveness of the Problem Based Learning model and the use of GeoGebra in learning, further research is needed in its integration. Therefore, this study aims to obtain empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning models on students' spatial visualization skills.

II. METHODS

This research is a quantitative research with a pre-experimental design in the form of a one-group pretest-posttest design. This study aims to test the effectiveness of GeoGebra-assisted problem-based learning models on spatial visualization capabilities. Research with this design was carried out with pretest and posttest. This research was conducted on grade IX students of SMP Negeri 3 Bintan in the 2025/2026 school year. The samples in this study were selected by cluster random sampling technique, which is a random selection based on class groups. Based on the results of randomization, class IX F was determined as a class that applied a problem based learning model assisted by GeoGebra.

The data collection technique was carried out using test instruments, which consisted of pretest and posttest to measure students' spatial visualization abilities in the form of an essay test. The previously developed research instruments were tested for validity and reliability. After the instrument used is declared valid and reliable, the instrument is used in the research. The data of the research results were analyzed by descriptive data analysis techniques and inferential data analysis using the one sample t-test with an assumption test that must be met. Inferential testing is carried out with the help of the R Studio program.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Description of Research Implementation

Learning activities on the building material of flat side rooms in this study were carried out four times in each

class. The implementation of each meeting in class IX F that applies the GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning model is presented as follows.

Table I Implementation of Learning with GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning Model

The meeting	Percentage of Activity	
	Teacher	Student
1	92,85%	92,85%
2	96,42%	96,42%
3	96,42%	96,42%
4	100%	100%
Average	96,42%	96,42%

Based on Table I above, the implementation of learning with the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model assisted by GeoGebra shows that the average implementation of teacher and student activities reached 96.42% in the very good category. This shows that the learning steps listed in the teaching module have been implemented optimally during the learning process.

Spatial Visualization Capability Data Description

The test data on students' spatial visualization ability was obtained from the results of students' work in the pretest and posttest. The following are presented the results of the spatial visualization ability test in Table II below.

Table II Spatial Visualization Capability Data Description

Description	Spatial Visualization Capability Data	
	Teacher	Student
Lots of Data	35	35
Average	52,97	85,47
Standard Deviation	7,06	5,793
Minimum Score	37,50	72,92
Maximum Score	66,67	93,75
Ideal Minimum Values	0	0
Ideal Maximum Value	100	100

Based on Table II above, students' spatial visualization skills have increased after being given learning treatments, where the average spatial visualization ability increased by 32.50, which is from 52.97 in the pretest stage to 85.47 in the posttest stage. The data on students' spatial visualization abilities are then grouped into predetermined categories, namely "very high", "high", "medium", and "low". The results of the grouping of students' spatial visualization abilities are presented as follows.

Table III Categorization of Students' Spatial Visualization Abilities

Value Interval	Spatial Visualization Capability Data				Category
	Pretest		Posttest		
	f	%	f	%	
$91 \leq x \leq 100$	0	0%	7	20%	Very High
$83 \leq x < 91$	0	0%	19	54,28%	High
$75 \leq x < 83$	0	0%	7	20%	Medium
$0 \leq x < 75$	35	100%	2	5,71%	Low

Based on Table III above, at the pretest stage, there were no students who reached the medium, high, or very high categories. These findings suggest that students' initial spatial visualization abilities are still at low levels. After being given learning treatment, there was a significant change in the category of spatial visualization ability, namely as many as 2 students (5.71%) were still in the low category. Meanwhile, 7 students (20.00%) are in the medium category, 19 students (54.28%) are in the high category, and 7 students (20.00%) have reached the very high category. These results showed that most of the students experienced an improvement in spatial visualization skills to reach the high and very high categories after the treatment was given.

Data Analysis

Before conducting a hypothesis test to determine the effectiveness of GeoGebra's problem-based learning model on spatial visualization capabilities, an assumption test was first carried out. The assumption test in this study includes a normality test. The normality test was carried out on spatial visualization ability data using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The results of the pretest and posttest data normality test of spatial visualization ability are presented as follows.

Table IV Data Normality Test Results

Data	W	p-value	Conclusion
Before Treatment	0,974	0,578	Normally
After Treatment	0,944	0,719	Distributed

Based on Table IV above, the p-value in the Shapiro-Wilk test for students' spatial visualization ability data shows a value greater than 0.05, both in the pre- and post-treatment stages. The result shows that H0 is accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that the data of students' spatial visualization abilities come from a normally distributed population.

After the assumption of normality is met, the next stage is to conduct a hypothesis test on the data on students' spatial visualization ability. To determine the effectiveness of learning with the GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning (PBL) model, a test was carried out on the posttest

data of students' spatial visualization skills. The statistical test uses the One Sample t-Test. Test results show $t_{count} = 10,707 > t_{table} = 1,690$ and $p\text{-value} = 0,000000000000985 < 0,05$ so that H_0 rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning (PBL) models are effective from the spatial visualization ability.

The development of students' spatial visualization skills is closely related to the selection of learning models and learning media used by teachers. The right learning model can build a learning environment that encourages students to think actively, explore concepts, and participate directly in the learning process. In addition, the use of technology-based learning media also helps students understand abstract mathematical concepts through more concrete and interactive visual presentations. In addition to testing hypotheses, it is also important to see how students arrive at their answers in working on the spatial visualization ability test questions.

Figure I Sample Student Answer to Question Number 1

Figure I above shows that the mental manipulation indicator is able to determine the change in the position of the cube side after rotating 180° clockwise. Students can identify the initial position of the front, back, left, right, top, and bottom sides, and infer the change in side position appropriately. This shows that students are able to mentally imagine changes in the position of building the space correctly. In the mental transformation indicator, students were able to describe the cube nets according to the position of the label before the rotation. Students also provide

information on each side according to the information provided, thus demonstrating the ability to transform three-dimensional space into a two-dimensional representation well.

In the spatial relationship indicator, students are able to determine the position relationship between sides when a student stands facing one side of the cube. Students explain the positions in front, back, left, and right based on the observer's point of view, and deduce the position of the other side appropriately. This answer shows that students are able to understand the positional relationships between the elements of building space consistently. In the spatial orientation indicator, students are able to determine the side that is in front of the teacher when the teacher stands on the back side of the cube. Students stated that the side in front of the teacher was the opposite side to the position of the teacher standing, namely the "Let's Donate" side. This explanation shows that students are able to recognize the position of the building space from the perspective of different observers.

Figure II Sample Student Answers to Question Number 2

Figure II above shows that in the mental manipulation indicator, students were able to determine the change in the position of the side of the beam after rotating 90° clockwise. Students stated that in the initial condition the front side was written "Care for Others", and after the block was turned, the front side moved to the right side. This answer shows that students are able to mentally imagine changes in the position of the side of the beam due to rotation correctly. In the spatial transformation indicator, students were able to describe the beam nets based on the size given and place the label "Care for Others" on the appropriate side. This indicates that students are able to transform the representation of three-dimensional spatial buildings into two-dimensional forms precisely.

In the spatial relationship indicator, students are able to determine the position of the side of the block when a teacher or resident is standing on the back side of the cardboard. The students concluded that the side in front of the teacher was the front side of the cardboard, which was

the side that said "Care for Others". In the spatial orientation indicator, students are able to determine the side in front of the resident's body when the resident stands on the left side of the cardboard and faces towards the cardboard. The students concluded that the side in front of the residents was the left side of the cardboard itself.

Figure III Sample Student Answers to Question Number 3

Figure 3 shows that in the mental manipulation indicator, students were able to imagine a change in the position of the pencil holder when placed from a sleeping position (horizontal) to standing upright. The students concluded that when the triangular base touches the surface of the table, then one of the rectangular-shaped upright sides that has a zipper will be the front side. This reasoning shows that students are able to visualize changes in orientation to build space mentally appropriately. The same thing in the indicators of spatial transformation, spatial orientation and spatial relations of students can be fulfilled overall well.

Based on the sample of students' answers as a whole, it can be seen that learning with a problem based learning model assisted by GeoGebra has the potential to facilitate students' spatial visualization skills. These findings are in line with Battista (2007) who stated that mental manipulation skills develop through active interaction with visual representations, and are supported by the research of Juandi & Priatna (2018) who found that the use of GeoGebra is able to significantly improve students' visual thinking skills. Santika (2019) in the study also showed that the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model contributes positively to the ability of spatial visualization in the context of geometry problem solving. These findings are in line with the opinion of Arends (2012) who states that problem-based learning encourages learners to associate various representations and concepts, and is supported by research by Sugiarni et al. (2018) who found an improvement in mathematical spatial skills through visual media-assisted learning. Thus, the integration of GeoGebra-assisted Problem Based Learning models not only provides a more interactive learning experience, but is also able to create a learning environment that supports the optimal development

of students' spatial visualization skills. Learning that combines contextual problem-solving and dynamic visualization allows students to build more meaningful spatial understanding, thus contributing positively to improving the quality of geometry learning.

IV. CONCLUSION

The use of GeoGebra-assisted problem-based learning models has proven to be effective in facilitating students' spatial visualization skills. This is supported by a significant increase in posttest scores compared to pretest results, with an increase of 32.50 with an average percentage of learning implementation reaching 96.42%. Thus, the integration of the problem based learning model and GeoGebra is able to support students in developing their abilities. Practically, the use of GeoGebra makes learning more interesting and meaningful. Students are also more encouraged in learning activities that support the understanding of the concepts learned. Further research is needed to find out how learning with GeoGebra-assisted problem-based learning models is effective on spatial visualization abilities at different levels and materials.

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